

THE CYANINE DYES OF THE PYRIDINE SERIES. PART V.

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p-Dimethylamino- and *p*-diethylamino-benzaldehydes have been condensed with α -, β - and γ -picoline-methiodide and the chemical, dyeing and photographic properties of the compounds, thus produced, examined. The influence of the change in position of the attachment of the dialkylamino-benzaldehyde residue to the pyridine ring has also been discussed.

In the valuable photographic sensitiser (S), first prepared by Pope and Mills (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 946), the effect of change of the alkyl radical attached to

(S)

the tertiary and the quaternary nitrogen atoms, and the acid radical, on the sensitising characteristics of the compound has been reported in previous papers of this series (Doja, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 347; Doja *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1942, 19, 125, 377; 1946, 23, 117). In the present work, the influence of the change in the position of attachment of the *p*-dialkylaminobenzaldehyde residue to the pyridine ring has been investigated. α -, β - and γ -Picoline-methiodides have been condensed with *p*-dimethylamino- and *p*-diethylamino-benzaldehydes and the resulting dyestuffs examined. For a good yield it is essential that the constituents should be completely dry, and the condensation carried out in the absence of moisture. Two sets of compounds, (A, B, C) and (A₁, B₁, C₁) have been prepared. The first set has been obtained by the condensation of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde with α -picoline-methiodide (A), β -picoline-methiodide (B) and γ -picoline-methiodide (C) respectively, and the second set by the condensation of *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde with α -picoline-methiodide (A₁), β -picoline-methiodide (B₁) and γ -picoline-methiodide (C₁). Some of the properties of these compounds are recorded in Table I.

Although A (Pope and Mills, *loc. cit.*) and A₁ (Doja and Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 125) have been described before, they have been prepared again under conditions similar to the other compounds and their properties included for the sake of comparison.

In each set, it will be seen, the *ortho* compound (A and A₁) has the highest and the *meta* compound (B and B₁), the lowest melting points.

It is noteworthy that the yields of these compounds are very high, whereas cyanine dyes usually give poor yields.

TABLE I

Compound.	Colour & shape of crystals.	M.p.	Yield.	Reflex.	Pleochroism.		Relative resistance to decolorisation.		Relative intensity of colour in solution.	Extra sensitisation		Remarks.
					position One.	⊥ position.	Aq. soln.	Alcoholic soln.		Ranges in Å	Maximum in Å	
A	Vermilion red, needles	265°	82.9%	Blue	Yellowish red	Nearly opaque	7.2	22.1	1	4800-6100	5500	Ortho
B	Dark chocolate, microscopic crystals	247°	81.8	Very weak blue	Amethyst (very weak)	Dark red	7.9	18.2	14.55	4800-6300	5600	Meta
C	Vermilion, tiny felted needles	261.5°	76.1	Weak blue	Orange	Blood red	6.6	18.6	1.01	4800-5900	5400	Para
A ₁	Light mauve, flattened needles	240°	76.1	Strong scintillating light blue	Deep pink	Nearly opaque	1	8.2	2.01	4850-6000	5450	Ortho
B ₁	Light chocolate, stunted needles	222°	83.5	Green	Bright cherry red	Nearly opaque	1.4	9.1	28.87	4800-6350	5600	Meta
C ₁	Mauve, stout needles	232.5	86.3	Strong scintillating blue	Orange-red	Bluish red	1.2	7.1	1.79	4800-5900	5400	Para

In conformity with the observations of Mills and Pope (*Phot. J.*, 1920, 44, 255), it has been found that these dyes are decolorised by the addition of mineral acid both in aqueous and alcoholic solutions, the latter being more resistant than the former. The "Relative resistance to decolorisation", shown in Table I, has been determined by finding the value of $N/100\text{-HCl}$ required to decolorise 2 c.c. of 1/100,000 solution of the dyes, and dividing the figures, thus obtained, by the smallest among these. It will be noticed that the compounds of the first set in the dimethylamino dyes are more resistant to decolorisation than those of the second set in the diethylamino dyes. The colour produced on silk, wool and cotton, when dyed with these compounds, is given in Table II. There is little difference in shade by the use of a neutral or an acid bath. The best shade is produced on wool, and this has the maximum resistance to fading too, comparatively speaking. Like other cyanine dyes, colour of these compounds also is neither fast to sunlight nor to washing. All these compounds produce beautiful crystals, which are freely soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and water, forming light orange coloured solutions in the case of A, C and A₁, C₁ and cherry-red solutions in the case of B and B₁. The alcoholic solution in each case, is clearer and more deeply coloured than the corresponding aqueous solution. The *meta* dyes, B and B₁, are less soluble in these solvents than the *ortho* and *para* dyes, A, A₁ and C, C₁. The

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

compounds are all insoluble in ether, benzene and chloroform. The "Relative intensity of colour" in alcoholic solutions (1 : 1000), determined in the usual way by means of a Duboscq colorimeter, is given in Table I. The higher intensity of the two *meta* compounds (B, B₁) and the large difference between them are noteworthy.

The fluorescence of weak alcoholic solution (1 : 100,000) of these dyes is given in Table III (*cf.* Doja, *loc. cit.*).

In Figures 1, 2 are shown the absorption and sensitisation spectra of these compounds and in Table I are given the ranges and maxima of the extra sensitisation bands.

It will be noticed that both the *meta* compounds, B and B₁, are powerful "Green" sensitisers; in the quality, they surpass even the compound prepared by Mills and Pope (*loc. cit.*). The extra sensitisation bands are intense, uniform and "blue-green-gap"-free. As is to be expected, the heavier compound B₁, has a slightly longer band of extra sensitisation.

TABLE II

Compound.	Colour produced on		
	Silk.	Wool.	Cotton.
A	Saffron	Orange-yellow	Turmeric-yellow
B	Beetroot red	Dirty magenta	Magenta
C	Bright orange-yellow	Deep orange-yellow	Dull brownish yellow
A ₁	Bright orange-yellow	Deep orange-yellow	Dull brownish yellow
B ₁	Bluish red	Deep bluish red	Weak bluish red
C ₁	Orange-yellow	Deep orange-yellow	Dull yellow

So far as this series goes, our investigations show, that among the *ortho*-, *para*- and *meta*- dyes of the same type, the *meta* compound is the most powerful sensitiser. Why is this so is a question, which has yet to be answered. In view of the well known similarity between the *ortho* and the *para* positions, the resemblance in properties recorded in this paper, between A, C and A₁, C₁ on the one hand, and B and B₁ on the other, is interesting.

EXPERIMENTAL

The absolute alcohol used in these experiments, was in each case, freshly redistilled over quicklime and tested water-free, before being used. The picolines were all purified through their picrates, before quaternisation.

2-*p*-Dimethylaminostyryl-pyridine-methyl iodide (A) was prepared according to the method of Mills and Pope (*loc. cit.*) (Found : I, 34.34. C₁₈H₁₇N₂I requires I, 34.69 per cent).

3-*p*-Dimethylaminostyryl-pyridine-methyl iodide (B) was prepared by heating together β-picoline-methiodide (0.4 g.), *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.4 g.), piperidine (5 drops) and absolute alcohol (8.5 c.c.), to a brisk boil for five hours. The reaction mixture turned yellow, then orange and finally deep orange; and on cooling, the separated crystals were filtered washed with alcohol-ether and recrystallised from methyl alcohol, yield 0.509 g. (Found : I, 34.48. C₁₈H₁₇N₂I requires I, 34.69 per cent).

4-*p*-Dimethylaminostyryl-pyridine-methyl iodide (C).—*p*-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.29 g.), γ -picoline-methiodide (0.41 g.) and piperidine (6 drops) were dissolved in absolute alcohol (9 c.c.) and the solution refluxed for 6 hours. The solution on cooling deposited crystals, which were recrystallised from absolute methyl alcohol, yield, 0.480 g. (Found : I, 34.51. $C_{16}H_{16}N_2I$ requires I, 34.69 per cent).

2-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-pyridine-methiodide (A_1) was obtained by the method of Doja and Prasad (*loc. cit.*). (Found : I, 32.19. $C_{18}H_{22}N_2I$ requires I, 32.23 per cent).

3-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-pyridine-methiodide (B_1) was prepared by heating a solution of *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.35 g.), β -picoline methiodide (0.40 g.) and piperidine (5 drops) in absolute alcohol (8.5 c.c.) on a water-bath for 5 hours. The deep red solution, thus obtained, was cooled, and the separated crystals, recrystallised from methyl alcohol, yield 0.56 g. (Found : I, 32.15. $C_{18}H_{22}N_2I$ requires I, 32.23 per cent).

TABLE III

Wallace colour filter No.	Colour of the fluorescent beam seen at right angles to the incident beam					
	A	B	C	A_1	B_1	C_1
1	Weak red	Light absorbed	Cherry red	Weak red	Crimson red	Light absorbed
2	Weak red	Rose red	Weak red	Crimson red	Pink	Rose red
3	Greenish yellow	Claret red	Dull yellow	Pink	Weak red	Grass green
4	Faint pink	Pink	Light absorbed	Reddish yellow	Rose red	Weak rose red
5	Dull yellow	Yellowish pink	Yellow	Weak yellow	Cherry red	Yellow
6	Dull yellow	Rose red	Weak yellow	Do	Very weak red	Yellow
7	Dull yellow with an orange tinge	Dull yellow	Lemon yellow	Grass green	Claret red	Dull yellow
8	Do	Yellowish red	Reddish yellow	Weak green	Orange	Yellowish orange
9	Yellow	Absorbed	Grass green	Weak bluish green	Light absorbed	Lemon yellow
10	Yellow	Orange	Bottle green	Weak orange	Weak red	Greenish

4-*p*-Diethylaminostyryl-pyridine-methyl iodide (C_1) was obtained by refluxing together *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.35 g.), γ -picoline-methiodide (0.47 g.) and piperidine (1 c.c.) dissolved in absolute alcohol (8.5 c.c.) for 5 hours. Within a few minutes the solution became red and crystals began to separate. These were filtered out, after cooling, and recrystallised from methyl alcohol, yield 0.68 g. (Found : I, 32.19, $C_{18}H_{22}N_2I$ requires 32.23 per cent).